

Event-triggered Prescribed-time Time-varying Formation Tracking Control of Nonlinear Multi-agent Systems

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the event-triggered prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking problem of nonlinear multi-agent systems. Firstly, a triggering mechanism is proposed. Then, a new event-triggered prescribed-time protocol is constructed to achieve time-varying formation tracking control in the prescribed time. Furthermore, using Lyapunov stability theory, the stability of systems is proved in detail, which implies that the nonlinear multi-agent systems can achieve prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking control. Moreover, it proves the Zeno behavior can be avoided by choosing parameters appropriately. Finally, the theoretical results of this paper are verified through a numerical simulation example.

Keywords

Prescribed-time; Time-varying formation; Event-triggered; Nonlinear multi-agent systems

1. Introduction

In the past decade, distributed cooperative control problems of multi-agent systems have developed rapidly. As a fundamental and important field of multi-agent systems (MASs), formation control has been extensively investigated [1-4]. Compared to time-invariant formation, the shape of time-varying formation can continuously change over time, which is more popular in many practical applications [5-8]. In the above work, communication among agents and continuous controller updates are necessary, because of the limitations in communication and control resources, this approach is often impractical in many real occasions. Then, event-triggered control strategies have been introduced, which can significantly conserve resources [9-12]. Distributed event-triggered adaptive output feedback control strategy is designed to make continuous monitoring of the measurement error no longer needed [13]. The adaptive method and fuzzy logic systems are employed to approximate unknown nonlinear functions in robotic dynamics [14]. The adaptive event-triggered control problem was discussed for a class of nonlinear systems [17]. In the research of multi-agent systems, the event-triggered mechanism is important and challenging.

Convergence time is an important performance index in formation control. In this context, finite-time control has gained popularity due to its high precision, fast convergence, and strong robustness against disturbances and parameter uncertainties [16-18]. Many control tactics have been proposed to solve the finite-time formation control issues. For example, the finite-time rigidity-based formation maneuvering control was studied for single integrator MASs [19]. Additionally, a novel integral sliding mode-based robust finite-time event-triggered control protocol was put forward to address the formation control of multi-robot systems [20]. It can be observed that the convergence time derived from the above-mentioned control technologies depends on the initial conditions of the agents. It is unfavorable in practical situations due to the fact that the convergence time can grow unboundedly when the initial conditions increase. To overcome the limitations of finite-time control, fixed-time control has garnered significant attention [21-24]. Fixed-time control features a well-defined convergence time that does not depend on the initial conditions of the system, making it superior in applications

that require high precision and rapid response. Some typical works on fixed-time consensus control have been reported. The fixed-time tracking problem of time-varying formations under an event-triggered mechanism is proposed in [25]. Another paper proposes an event-triggered adaptive fixed-time control strategy of uncertain nonlinear systems [26]. However, finite-time control depends on the initial state of the system, fixed-time control depends on the system parameters. Different from finite-time control and fixed-time control, the convergence time of prescribed-time control can be precisely predetermined by users as an arbitrary expected constant, which is independent of the initial state of the system and controller parameters [27-30]. Therefore, prescribed-time control significantly enhances the convergence performance of multi-agent systems.

Besides, compared with linear multi-agent systems, nonlinear multi-agent systems have richer connotations and broader applicability in both theoretical research and many practical applications [31-33]. Based on the above discussion, this article comprehensively studies the event-triggered prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking of nonlinear multi-agent systems.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Some useful preliminaries are given in Section 2. Section 3 provides distributed prescribed-time control algorithms and the system stability analysis. Simulation results are given in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusion.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Graph theory

The information communication relationship between one leader and N followers is described by the communication topology $\bar{G} = G \cup \{0\}$. Let 0 denote the leader, and $G = \{0, \varepsilon, A\}$ denote the information communication between N followers. $\mathcal{G} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is the nodes set, $\varepsilon \subseteq \mathcal{G} \times \mathcal{G}$ represents the set of edges and $A = [a_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ with $a_{ii} = 0$ is the adjacency matrix. In $A = [a_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $a_{ij} > 0$ indicates that the i agent can receive information from the j agent, otherwise, $a_{ij} = 0$. $B = \text{diag}(a_{10}, a_{20}, \dots, a_{N0})$ denotes the adjacency matrix between the leader and N followers. Moreover, The Laplacian matrix $L = [l_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is defined as $l_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij}$ and $l_{ij} = -a_{ij}$ for $i \neq j$. Define $H = L + B$, if there is at least one node with a directed path to all other nodes, the communication graph \bar{G} contains a directed spanning tree.

Notations. \mathbb{R}^n and $\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ represent the real matrices with $n \times 1$ and $n \times m$ dimensions, respectively. \mathbb{R} is the set of real numbers. \mathbb{R}_+ denotes the positive real number set. For a symmetric matrix o , the respective maximum and minimum eigenvalues are represented by the notations $\lambda_{\max}(o)$ and $\lambda_{\min}(o)$. The diagonal matrix is denoted as $\text{diag}(\cdot)$. \otimes represents the Kronecker product. $\|\cdot\|_p$ is represented as the p -norm for vectors or matrices. $\text{sign}(\cdot)$ represents the sign function. 1_N denotes the N dimensional column vector with entries all being 1. $|\cdot|$ represents the absolute value.

2.2. Problem formulation

Consider the nonlinear multi-agent systems including one leader and N followers. The dynamics of the i agent are described as

$$\dot{x}_i(t) = f(x_i(t), t) + w(x_i(t), t) + u_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N, \tag{1}$$

where $x_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is state, $u_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the control input, $w(x_i(t), t)$ is the external disturbances.

The leader has the following dynamic

$$\dot{x}_0(t) = f(x_0(t), t), \tag{2}$$

where $x_0(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state of leader, and $f : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is the nonlinear dynamic.

2.3 Some useful lemmas and definitions

A time scale function is constructed as follows in order to achieve the prescribed-time time-varying control

$$\mu(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{T^h}{(T + t_0 - \theta t)^h}, & t \in [t_0, t_1), \\ 1, & t \in [t_1, \infty). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

With $h > 1, T > 0, 0 < \theta < 1$, and $t_0 > 0, t_1 = t_0 + T$, t_0 and T are the initial time and the preselected constant. Suppose that the initial time is $t_0 = 0$, then $t_1 = T$. At this point, the original time-varying function can be modified to the following form

$$\mu(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{T^h}{(T - \theta t)^h}, & t \in [0, T), \\ 1, & t \in [T, \infty). \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In equation (3), the time-varying scaling function $\mu(t)$ is utilized in the controller, in which $\mu(t) = \frac{T^h}{(T - t)^h}$ for $t \in [0, T)$, this may make the controller $u_i(t)$ unbounded. Because the function $\frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)}$ grows to infinity when t approaches T . In this paper, a new time-varying function (4) is introduced to prevent the gain from becoming infinite over the desired convergence time T , additionally, it is able to boost the convergence accuracy. In equation (4), $\lim_{t \rightarrow T} \mu^{\frac{1}{h}}(t)$ is bounded.

Consider the following system

$$\dot{y}(t) = f(t, y(t)), y_0 = y(0), \quad (5)$$

where $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the state, $f(t, y(t)): \mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is a nonlinear vector bounded in time, y_0 is the initial state.

Lemma 1: There exists a Lyapunov function $V(y)$ for (5) such that

$$\dot{V}(y) \leq -\alpha_1 V(y) - \alpha_2 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)} V(y), \quad t \in [t_0, t_0 + T), \quad (6)$$

where $c, k > 0$ then the origin of system (5) is globally prescribed-time stable with the prescribed-time $t_0 + T$.

Especially, the following solution can be obtained

$$\begin{cases} V(y) \leq \mu(t)^{-\alpha_2} \exp^{-\alpha_1(t-t_0)} V(y_0), & t \in [t_0, t_0 + T), \\ V(y) \equiv 0, & t \in [t_0 + T, \infty). \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Lemma 2: Let $k_1, k_2, \dots, k_M \geq 0$ be nonnegative numbers, then

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^M k_i\right)^s \leq \sum_{i=1}^M k_i^s \leq M^{1-s} \left(\sum_{i=1}^M k_i\right)^s, \quad 0 < s \leq 1, \quad (8)$$

$$M^{1-s} \left(\sum_{i=1}^M k_i\right)^s \leq \sum_{i=1}^M k_i^s \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^M k_i\right)^s, \quad 1 < s < \infty. \quad (9)$$

Definition 1: The prescribed-time event-triggered time-varying formation tracking for nonlinear MASs (1) and (2) is achieved if the distributed controller $u_i(t)$ is designed such that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow T} \|x_i(t) - x_0(t) - h_i(t)\| = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\|x_i(t) - x_0(t) - h_i(t)\| = 0, \quad \forall t > T, \quad (11)$$

for any initial states $x_i(t)$ and $x_0(t)$. Moreover, T is the prescribed time, $h_i(t)$ is the continuously differentiable formation vector.

Assumption 1: For any $x_i(t), x_j(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the nonlinear dynamic satisfies Lipschitz conditions

$$\|f(x_i(t), t) - f(x_j(t), t)\| \leq \rho \|x_i(t) - x_j(t)\|, \quad (12)$$

ρ is a positive constant to be determined.

Assumption 2: $w(x_i(t), t)$ is bounded, satisfying $\|w(x_i(t), t)\| \leq \tilde{w}$, in which \tilde{w} is a positive constant.

3. Main result

In this section, we will consider the nonlinear MASs (1) and (2) to achieve prescribed-time time-varying

tracking. In order to reduce the communication burden, a novel distributed event-triggered control strategy is adopted.

The prescribed-time event-triggered controller is designed as follows

$$u_i(t) = -(k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t_k^i)) - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t_k^i)) + \dot{h}_i(t), \tag{13}$$

where

$$y_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij}(x_j(t) - h_j(t) - (x_j(t) - h_j(t_k^j))) + b_i(x_i(t) - x_0(t) - h_i(t)), \tag{14}$$

$k, c, k_1, k_2 > 0$ are design parameters, and t_k^i is the k_{th} triggering time instant of agent i . Next, the triggering mechanism is constructed as

$$t_{k+1}^i = \inf\{t > t_k^i : \|E_i(t)\| > \eta_1 \|y_i(t)\| + \eta_2 \sigma(t)\}, \tag{15}$$

where the measurement error is

$$E_i(t) = (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t_k^i)) + k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t_k^i)) - (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t)) - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t)), \tag{16}$$

and $\sigma(t)$ is defined as $\sigma(t) = \mu^{-\varphi}(t)$ and $\sigma(t) = 0$ at $t \in [0, t_0 + T)$ and $t \in [t_0 + T, \infty)$. respectively, η_1, η_2, φ are positive constants to be designed. Then the prescribed-time time-varying tracking problem can be achieved under the controller (13).

Theorem 1: For System (1) and (2), if Assumptions 1-2 hold and the control parameters $c > 0, k > 0$, and k, k_2 satisfy

$$k > \frac{\rho}{k_1 \lambda_{\min}(H)} + \frac{\eta_1}{k_1}, \quad k_2 \geq \tilde{w} + \eta_2 \sigma(t), \tag{17}$$

then the prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking problem can be achieved under the distributed event-triggered control protocol (13).

Proof: Let $\tau_i(t) = x_i(t) - x_0(t) - h_i(t)$, and $\tau(t) = [\tau_1^T(t), \tau_2^T(t), \dots, \tau_n^T(t)]^T$. By selecting the Lyapunov function candidate as

$$V(t) = \frac{1}{2} \tau^T(t) (H \otimes I_n) \tau(t). \tag{18}$$

The derivative of $V(t)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) (f(x_i(t), t) + w_i(x_i(t), t) - f(x_0(t), t) - (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i^T(t_k^i)) - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i^T(t_k^i))), \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) (f(x_i(t), t) + w_i(t, x_i(t)) - E_i(t) - (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t)) - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t)) - f(x_0(t), t)). \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

We can obtain

$$\|\tau_i(t)\|_2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2}}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} \leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2}{\lambda_{\min}(H)}. \tag{20}$$

Then based on assumption 1

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) (f(x_i(t), t) - f(x_0(t), t)) &\leq \rho \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2 \|\tau_i(t)\|_2, \\ &\leq \frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

From assumption 2, we can obtain

$$\sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) w(x_i(t), t) \leq \tilde{w} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2. \tag{22}$$

Based on triggering condition (15), we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) E_i(t) > \eta_1 \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 + \eta_2 \sigma(t) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2. \tag{23}$$

From (21) and (22), it yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) &\leq \frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 + \tilde{w} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2 + \eta_1 \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 + \eta_2 \sigma(t) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2 \\ &\quad - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t) [(k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t) + k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t))), \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq (\frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} + \eta_1 - k k_1) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 - c k_1 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 + (\tilde{w} + \eta_2 \sigma(t) - k_2) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2. \end{aligned}$$

Since $2\lambda_{\min}(H)V(t) \leq \sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t)y_i(t) \leq 2\lambda_{\max}(H)$, it thus follows from (24) that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) &\leq -(k k_1 - \frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} - \eta_1) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 - c k_1 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2^2 - (k_2 - \tilde{w} - \eta_2 \sigma(t)) \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2, \\ &\leq -2\lambda_{\min}(H)(k k_1 - \frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} - \eta_1)V(t) - 2\lambda_{\min}(H)c k_1 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)}V(t), \\ &\leq -\alpha_1 V(t) - \alpha_2 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)}V(t), \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

where $\alpha_1 = 2\lambda_{\min}(H)(k k_1 - \frac{\rho}{\lambda_{\min}(H)} - \eta_1)$, $\alpha_2 = 2\lambda_{\min}(H)c k_1$. It can be obtained that the conditions (17) hold. It thus

concludes that $\dot{V}(t) \leq -\alpha_1 V(t) - \alpha_2 \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)}V(t)$. According to Lemma 1, it follows

$$V(t) \leq \mu(t)^{-\alpha_2} \exp^{-\alpha_1(t-t_0)} V(t_0). \tag{26}$$

For $t \geq T$, we have $\dot{V}(t) \leq -\alpha_1 V(t)$. It obtains $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\tau(t)\|_2 = 0$. For $t \in (T, \infty)$, it can be obtained that $V(t) \equiv 0$. Therefore, the prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking can be achieved by the above analysis process.

Theorem 2. Using event-triggered function (15) and control algorithm (13) to achieve prescribed-time time-varying formation tracking of system (1) and (2), in addition, the inter-event interval $\{t_{k+1}^i - t_k^i\}$ is bounded below by a positive constant, the Zeno-behavior will not happen.

For the case of $t \in [0, t_0 + T)$, under the definition of measurable errors $E_i(t)$, one gets

$$\begin{aligned} E_i(t) &= u_i(t) - u_i(t_k^i) \\ &= -(k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t) - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t))) + (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t_k^i) + k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t_k^i))), \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{E}_i(t)\|_2 &= \left\| -(k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})'(k_1 y_i(t)) - (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 y_i(t))' - k_2 \text{sign}(y_i(t))' \right\|_2 \\ &\leq \left\| \frac{ch\theta^2}{(T + t_0 - \theta t)^2} (k_1 y_i(t)) \right\|_2 + \left\| (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)})(k_1 \dot{y}_i(t)) \right\|_2 \\ &\leq \frac{k_1 ch\theta^2}{(T + t_0 - \theta t)^2} \|y_i(t)\|_2 + k_1 (k + c \frac{\dot{\mu}(t)}{\mu(t)}) \|\dot{y}_i(t)\|_2. \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

According to Lemma 2, we have

$$\|y_i(t)\|_2 \leq \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i(t)\|_2 \leq \sqrt{N} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i^T(t)y_i(t)} \leq \sqrt{N} \sqrt{2\lambda_{\max}(H)V(0)}. \tag{29}$$

Furthermore, based on the definition of $y_i(t)$, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{y}_i(t)\|_2 &= \left\| \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij}(\dot{x}_i(t) - \dot{h}_i(t) - (\dot{x}_j(t) - \dot{h}_j(t)) + b_i(\dot{x}_i(t) - \dot{h}_i(t) - \dot{x}_0(t)) \right\|_2 \\ &\leq \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} \|\dot{x}_i(t) - \dot{h}_i(t) - (\dot{x}_j(t) - \dot{h}_j(t))\|_2 + b_i \|\dot{x}_i(t) - \dot{h}_i(t) - \dot{x}_0(t)\|_2. \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

where h_j is the element of matrix H , combining with Theorem 2, we can get that $\tau_i(t)$ is bounded over the time interval $t \in [0, t_0 + T)$. And the continuously differentiable formation vector $h_i(t)$ is also bounded. there exists

positive constants $M, \partial_1, \partial_2$ such as $\|\tau_i(t)\|_2 \leq M$, $\|\dot{h}_i(t) - \dot{h}_j(t)\|_2 \leq \partial_1$, $\|\dot{h}_i(t)\|_2 \leq \partial_2$. Then we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{y}_i(t)\|_2 &\leq \left\| \sum_{j=1}^N h_{ij} u_j(t_{kj}^i) \right\|_2 + \rho \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} (\|\tau_i(t)\|_2 + \|\tau_j(t)\|_2) \\ &\quad + \rho b_i \|\tau_i(t)\|_2 + \tilde{w} (2 \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} + b_i) + \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} \|\dot{h}_i(t) - \dot{h}_j(t)\|_2 + b_i \|\dot{h}_i(t)\|_2 \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{j=1}^N h_{ij} u_j(t_{kj}^i) \right\|_2 + (M\rho + \tilde{w}) (\sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} + b_i) + \partial_1 \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} + \partial_2 b_i. \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Substituting (28) and (29), we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{E}_i(t)\|_2 &\leq \frac{k_1 ch\theta^2}{T + t_0 - \theta t} \sqrt{N} \sqrt{2\lambda_{\max}(H)V(t_0)} + k_1 \left(k + \frac{ch\theta}{T + t_0 - \theta t} \right) \|\dot{y}_i(t)\|_2 \\ &\leq z_1 \frac{ch\theta^2}{T^2} \mu^{\frac{2}{h}}(t) + z_2 \left(k + \frac{ch\theta}{T} \right) \mu^{\frac{1}{h}}(t), \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where $z_1 = k_1 \sqrt{N} \sqrt{2\lambda_{\max}(H)V(t_0)}$, $z_2 = k_1 \left(\left\| \sum_{j=1}^N h_{ij} u_j(t_{kj}^i) \right\|_2 + (M\rho + \tilde{w}) (\sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} + b_i) + \partial_1 \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} + \partial_2 b_i \right)$.

To demonstrate that Zeno behavior does not occur, it is necessary to prove that the growth of error is limited by the triggering interval, which means proving that the triggering interval has a positive lower bound $L > 0$. To prove that there exists a positive lower bound for the triggering interval, we can integrate with respect to $\|\dot{E}_i(t)\|_2$. Since $E_i(t_k^i) = 0$, it yields

$$\begin{aligned} \|E_i(t)\|_2 &\leq \int_{t_k^i}^t z_1 \frac{ch\theta^2}{T^2} \mu^{\frac{2}{h}}(s) + z_2 \left(k + \frac{ch\theta}{T} \right) \mu^{\frac{1}{h}}(s) ds + \|E_i(t_k^i)\|_2 \\ &\leq \int_{t_k^i}^{t_{k+1}^i} z_1 \frac{ch\theta^2}{T^2} \mu^{\frac{2}{h}}(s) + z_2 \left(k + \frac{ch\theta}{T} \right) \mu^{\frac{1}{h}}(s) ds. \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Since $\mu(t_{k+1}^i) \leq \frac{1}{(1-\theta)^h}$, Then Equation (33) can be rewritten as

$$\|E_i(t)\|_2 \leq L(t_{k+1}^i - t_k^i), \tag{34}$$

where $L = \left(z_1 \frac{ch\theta^2}{T^2} \frac{1}{(1-\theta)^h} + z_2 \left(k + \frac{ch\theta}{T} \right) \frac{1}{(1-\theta)^h} \right) > 0$.

According to the triggering condition (10), the next triggering instant t_{k+1}^i satisfy $L(t_{k+1}^i - t_k^i) \geq \eta_2 \sigma(t_{k+1}^i)$, $t_{k+1}^i - t_k^i \geq \frac{\eta_2 \sigma(t_{k+1}^i)}{L}$, $\sigma(t_{k+1}^i) > 0$, then Zeno behavior does not occur for $t \in [0, t_0 + T)$.

At this point, the triggering mechanism correspondingly becomes

$$t_{k+1}^i = \inf \{ t > t_k^i : \|E_i(t)\|_2 > \eta_1 \|y_i(t)\|_2 \}. \tag{35}$$

For $t \in [t_0 + T, \infty)$, the prescribed-time event-triggered time-varying problem transformed into the asymptotic time-varying problem based on the event-triggered. To prove that there is no Zeno behavior occurring in a general event-triggered mechanism of multi-agent systems, it is essential to demonstrate that the triggering interval has a positive lower bound. Exclusion methods for the Zeno phenomenon is similar to the analysis of [36] and is omitted here.

4. Numerical simulation

An example is proposed to verify the validity of the prescribed-time controller for time-varying control of the MASs. in the example, we consider a nonlinear multi-agent system with one leader and six followers, as shown in Figure 1. Number 0 represents the leader, and number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 represent the followers. The nonlinear dynamics are designed by $f(x_i(t), t) = [0.6 \sin(x_{i1}(t)), 0.8 \sin(x_{i2}(t))]^T$ and the disturbance are given as $w_i(x_i(t), t) = [0.1 \cos(x_{i1}(t)), 0.2 \cos(x_{i2}(t))]^T$.

By calculating, we can get $k = 1.5, k_1 = 0.5, k_2 = 0.1, c = 2.5, h = 2.1, \theta = 0.8, \lambda = 0.2$. We chose the prescribed-time $T=0.5s$. Based on the initial conditions and related parameters designed above, the result is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 represents the prescribed-time formation tracking error of six agents, $\bar{x}_i(t) = x_i(t) - x_0(t) - h_i(t)$. To better verify the results, we considered the case where the prescribed-time $T=1s$, figure 3 represents the prescribed-time formation tracking error of six agents.

Fig 1. Communication topology.

Fig 2. The formation tracking error of six agents (T=0.5s).

Fig 3. The formation tracking error of six agents (T=1s).

To achieve a time-varying formation, according to system (1) and (2) six followers will form a hexagonal shape and rotate around the leader, when time-varying formation is realized. Let the radius of the hexagon be r , with the six followers evenly distributed, and the angle between adjacent followers being 60 degrees. Figure 4 represents the time-varying formation graphs at different times. Figure 5 shows the trajectories of all agents. From Figure 4 and Figure 5 we can see the time-varying formation is achieved. Figure 6 shows the event-triggering instants of six agents, meaning no Zeno behavior occurs.

We use vector $h_i(t) = [h_1^T, h_2^T, h_3^T, h_4^T, h_5^T, h_6^T]^T$, to represent the state of these six followers in the desired time-varying formation. And we provide

$$h_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} r \sin(\omega t + \frac{(i-1)\pi}{3}) \\ r \cos(\omega t + \frac{(i-1)\pi}{3}) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $r=1.2$ is the formation radius, representing the distance from the leader to each follower, $\omega=1.5$ is the angular velocity for controlling the formation's rotation over time, enabling time-varying formation patterns.

Fig 4. State snapshots of the agents.

Fig 5. trajectories of all agents.

Fig 6. The triggering instants of six agents.

5 Conclusion

In the paper, we have addressed the prescribed-time event-triggered time-varying formation tracking problem of nonlinear multi-agent systems. An event-triggered prescribed-time control protocol was proposed. The proposed controller does not require continuous updates of the controller and continuous communication between neighboring agents. Moreover, it can achieve time-varying formation tracking. In addition, it is proven that the Zeno behavior can be excluded by choosing parameters appropriately. Finally, the validity of the theoretical conclusions was verified through a numerical simulation example. In future research, we will focus on studying the realization of prescribed-time event-triggered time-varying formation control using the sliding mode method.

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